

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF MECHANICALLY FLEXIBLE THREE-DIMENSIONAL GRAPHENE/POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES FOR MULTIFUNCTIONAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Graphene and graphene nanoribbon (GNR) have been incorporated into a wide range of polymer matrixes to fabricate nanocomposites with improved electrical, thermal, and mechanical properties [1-4]. Especially, integration of a 2D building block into macroscopic three-dimensional (3D) porous structures represents an effective way to translate the performance of individual graphene or GNR sheets to multifunctional nanocomposite materials [5]. The GNR-based nanocomposites have demonstrated great promise for a broad range of applications in the fields of mechanical reinforcement, supercapacitors, separation, and flexible electronics [6]. However, the previous 3D GNR based composites still exhibited poor structural stability and hydrophobic properties, e.g. easy brittleness and low water contact angle (<150°), limiting their practical applications in strain sensors and oil/water separation fields. Hence, it is still a challenge to fabricate 3D porous GNR based polymer composites with excellent mechanical flexibility and multi-functionality by using a facile and scalable method.

Here we described a facile low-cost and scalable-compatible dip-coating strategy for the fabrication of macroscopic porous graphene nanoribbon (GNR) based polymer foam nanocomposite materials with tunable surface chemistry and multi-functionality (Figure 1). Different concentrations of GONR aqueous solution was used to adjust the rGONR network formed on the commercial polyurethane (PU) sponge skeleton, and the microstructure and functional properties of 3D porous GNR nanocomposites can be controlled/tuned through introduction of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) coating or silane surface modification. The lightweight 3D porous GNR nanocomposites provide super mechanical performance (90% reversible compressibility), outstanding cyclic resilient property (full recovery after 100 cycles), good electrical conductivity (0.001-1 S m⁻¹), extremely high sensitivity of elasticity-dependent conductivity, excellent hydrophobicity (water contact angle >150 °C and fast water sliding phenomenon), and outstanding oil/water separation efficiency. Furthermore, compared to the rGONR@PU composite sample with poor water/oil separation efficiency, these porous silane-f-rGONR@PU composites not only possessed selective oil/water separation and excellent oil/solvent absorption capacity at static state, but also showed good continuous oil/solvent pumping collection with high recyclability (>95% after 10th cycles) and outstanding oil/water separation efficiency at the intensive dynamic shaking state. This opens new opportunities for the preparation of flexible and

lightweight 3D porous GNR nanocomposite materials with tunable functionalities, showing promising application in strain sensor and oil pollution remediation fields at different environmental conditions.

Figure 1. Fabrication process and microstructures of 3D porous rGONR-coated PU foam composites: (a) fabrication procedure of 3D porous rGONR-coated PU foam composites, and (c-d) SEM images of surface morphologies of 3D porous rGONR-based composites.

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